

SPECIFIC STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING READING SKILLS AMONG EFL STUDENTS

¹Rahmonova Ch.F

Master's degree student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University,

²Djalilov M.M

Supervisor - senior teacher.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825082>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th April 2023

Accepted: 12th April 2023

Online: 13th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Principle, method, skills, experiment, context, skimmin, scanning, hints, analyses, strategy.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the main features of reading principles and the methods to teach learners' reading comprehension. To be a proficient reader, different kinds of skills that learners must have are also given. Additionally, the results and the overall conclusion of the experiment are introduced in this article.

According to the recent research we conducted among B1 learners, we realize that reading skills are the cognitive processes a reader uses to make sense of a text. People learn comprehension skills through education or instruction and some learn by direct experiences.¹ Proficient reading depends on the ability to recognize words quickly and effortlessly.² Fluent readers use most of their reading skills unconsciously and automatically. When faced with difficult text, fluent readers consciously and strategically apply these skills to understand. v.v.

There are several reading skills that students need to master to become proficient readers: extracting main ideas, reading for specific information, understanding text organization, predicting, checking, comprehension, inference, working with unfamiliar words, linking ideas, understanding complex sentences, understanding style writer and resume writing. But if adult students are psychologically prepared for reading and it is only about acquiring elementary reading skills, enriching vocabulary and mastering at least a few grammatical rules, then the situation is completely different. with young elementary readers.At any level, a learner needs the following skills to become a proficient reader:

- automatic, rapid. letter recognition.
- automatic, rapid word recognition.
- the ability to use context as an aid to comprehension.
- the ability to use context when necessary as a conscious aid to word recognition

When teaching reading, the following approaches should not be neglected:

1. Focus on one skill at a time. Explain the purpose of working on this skill and convince students of its importance for effective reading.

¹ Tompkins, E. (2011). Literacy in the Early Grades

² Adams, M (1994). [Beginning to read: thinking and learning about print](#)

2. Work on an example of using the skill as a class. Explain your thoughts aloud as you do the exercise.
3. Assign students to work in pairs on activities in which they practice using the same skill. Ask them to explain their thoughts to a friend as they work.
4. Discuss student responses with the whole class. Ask them to explain how they got the answers. Encourage polite disagreement and demand an explanation for any differences in their responses.
5. In the same class, as well as in subsequent classes, to develop in portions work on broad exercises aimed at developing the same skill with increasing complexity. Encourage students to work in pairs whenever possible.
6. Have individual students complete an activity using a skill to test their ability and confidence in using it.
7. In the following lessons, lead students to apply the skill, as well as previously learned skills, to a variety of texts.

Reading becomes effective when the teacher starts with words familiar to the students, uses simple structures, the board and flashcards, and emphasizes both recognizing and understanding the meaning of the word. For younger students, reading instruction should begin when the child can learn his native language. In addition, it is suggested to use some reading repetition or practice and monitor progress. Moreover, teachers should always be aware of the various problems of reading in a foreign language.

Learning to read is also based on several principles:

Principle 1: Reading is not a passive skill. Reading is an incredibly active activity. To do this successfully, we must understand what the words mean, see the pictures the words paint, understand the arguments, and decide if we agree with them. If we don't do this—and if the students don't—we're only scratching the surface of the text and quickly forgetting it.

Principle 2: Students should be involved in what they read. As with everything else in the classroom, students who are not engaged in reading the text, who are not actively interested in what they are doing, are unlikely to benefit from it. When they are really passionate about a topic or task, they get much more out of what is in front of them.

Principle 3: Students should be encouraged to respond to the content of the text they read, not just the language. Of course, it is important to study reading texts in terms of how they use language, how many paragraphs they contain, and how many times they use relative clauses. But the meaning, the message of the text is no less important, and we must give students the opportunity to somehow respond to this message. It is especially important that they are allowed to express their feelings about the topic, thereby provoking personal involvement in it and in the language.

Principle 4: Prediction is an important factor in reading. When we read texts in our own language, we often have a good idea of the content before actually reading it. Book covers give us a clue as to what's in the book, photos and headlines indicate what articles are about, and reports look like reports before we read a single word. The moment we receive that cue—the book cover, the headline, the page of text—our brain begins to predict what we're going to read. Expectations are raised and the active process of reading can begin. Teachers should

give students “hints” so they can also anticipate what’s coming. It will make them better and more engaged readers.

Principle 5: Match. the task to the topic. We could give them a menu and ask them to list the ingredients alphabetically. There may be reasons for both tasks, but at first glance they look a bit. silly. Once a decision has been made about what reading text the students will read, we need to choose good reading. assignments - the right kind of questions, exciting and useful puzzles, etc. The most interesting text can be undermined by boring and inappropriate questions; The most everyday passage can be made really exciting with imaginative and challenging. tasks.

The most important. skill for academic success and good reading is reading comprehension. A study. conducted in the United States found a strong. relationship between reading. literacy and an individual’s potential for. success in their personal and professional lives.³ The main goals of our research conducted in the conditions of the lyceum are to increase the reading performance of students and to find answers to current problems. The research process helps teachers analyse needs, document inquiries, analyse data, and make decisions that can lead to desired outcomes.

Simply the stages of this research are:

- Planning
- Acting
- Observing
- Reflecting

Research. shows that students improve understanding when they analyse what strategy they are using and how it helps make. meaning of the text.

Data analysis is the process. of reducing significant. amounts of data to make the information. meaningful. According to some scholars, three things happen in data analysis: the collected data is organized, then the data. is reduced. by summarizing and categorizing, patterns. and themes in the data identified and linked. The data analysis process of this study began with the analysis of the collected data. This was done by watching recorded. videos, reading. and reviewing student results.

The results of the reading awareness scale and my personal experience showed that our students did not have sufficient. knowledge of reading strategies at the beginning of the study. This. conclusion emerged as a result of pre-test results. Students lacked knowledge and practice in reading strategies, but their achievement improved. After extensive learning through presentations explaining. six key reading strategies along with reading practice. Initially, as researchers, we had some concerns. about how to implement the strategies in the classroom. The number of strategies was another obstacle, as students could confuse them.

Ten respondents of B1 level participated in the survey. Below, the diagram comparing pre- and post- results will be followed.

³ Block, C. & Israel, S. (2005). Reading first and beyond

Results of pre-test

Results of post-test

Pre- and post-test results compared

Being the researchers, I initially had some concerns about how to use the techniques in the classroom. Another challenge was the sheer quantity of techniques, which the pupils could have found perplexing. The effectiveness of pupils' use of reading comprehension tools was a further concern. The pupils were unfamiliar with these reading comprehension techniques. We had to lead and supervise the students at every stage of the procedure, notably for the questioning, inferring, and summarizing tactics, in order to overcome this scenario. After a thorough investigation, we saw an improvement in my students. Both my students and I found this study adventure to be quite fulfilling.

Another question was. about students' success in using reading comprehension. strategies. These reading. strategies were new to the students. To overcome this situation, we

had to guide and supervise the students in each step of the process, particularly in questioning, inference and generalization strategies. After intensive study, we experienced improvement in our students. This research trip was very beneficial for both our students and me. The results of the action research gave me confidence in how to integrate the strategies into our curriculum. As for the students, they understood the strategies better and their reading comprehension improved. The current study was a productive experiment; Now that we have seen an increased understanding of reading comprehension strategies and an improvement in my students' reading comprehension, we want to continue using these strategies in our curriculum.

It includes research philosophy, research approach, methods used for data collection and data analysis. First, it begins with a discussion of research methodology and determines the most appropriate methodology to be used. In this study, the qualitative research method was chosen as the most appropriate. This methodology allows for the collection of descriptive and qualitative data on the strategies used in the development of reading comprehension and their effectiveness. In addition, the chapter also explains the methods used to collect the data. Primary data is collected using observation.

In summary, reading is one of the complex processes of language learning, which involves the threefold process of the learner, the text, and the purpose of reading. Reading is an interactive, problem-solving process of making meaning from texts. The reading process includes pre-reading, reading, responding, learning, and applying procedures. Students must use multiple strategies simultaneously to extract meaning from texts.

References:

1. Block, C. & Israel, S. (2005). Reading first and beyond: The complete guide for teachers and literacy coaches. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
2. Harrison C. Methods of Teaching Reading: Key Issues in Research and Implications for Practice / C. Harrison // Interchange. - 1996. - №39. - P.1-16.
3. Johnson A. P. Teaching Reading and Writing / A. P. Johnson. - Lahman, NY, Toronto, Plymouth: Rowman and Littlefield Education, 2008. - 260 p.
4. Tompkins, E. (2011). Literacy in the Early Grades: A Successful Start for Prek-4 Readers and Writers. Allyn and Bacon.
5. Adams, M (1994). Beginning to read: thinking and learning about print. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.
6. Beatrice S. Teaching reading in a second Language / S. Beatrice, E. D. Mikulecky. - London: Pearson Education, 2008.
7. Hager A. Techniques for Teaching Beginning-Level Reading to Adults / A. Hager // Focus on Basics. - 2001. - №5. P 1-5.
8. Harmer J. How to teach English / J. Harmer. - London: Longman, 2001. - 199 p.